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Research Article

PAIN MANAGEMENT IN NURSING PRACTICE

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Article Received: November 2022 **Accepted:** November 2022 **Published:** December 2022**Abstract:**

Nurses must possess a high level of pain management skills, where their experience in the field is a key indicator of their ability to effectively manage pain. Not only do they hold a crucial position in the realm of pain management, but they also employ a variety of methods, both pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical, to address pain-related issues. Additionally, nurses are known to dedicate the most time to patients, thereby establishing their significance in assessing and treating pain. It is crucial for nurses to engage in ongoing education and training to enhance their understanding and implementation of pain management techniques. This continuous learning ensures the selection of appropriate tools and scales for pain assessment tailored to factors such as the patient's age, condition, and the specific clinical environment.

Keywords: pain, nurses, role.

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INTRODUCTION:

Pain management in nursing is a multifaceted and critical component of patient care, encompassing various strategies and settings. However, studies indicate that nurses often have inadequate knowledge and attitudes toward it. Competency in pain management is crucial, with work experience being a significant predictor of a nurse's ability to manage pain effectively. There is a pressing need for continuous education programs to enhance the skills of less experienced nurses. Prelicensure nursing education emphasizes the importance of clinical judgment and

critical thinking in pain evaluation and management, particularly in the context of the opioid crisis, highlighting the need for evidence-based strategies to alleviate pain and prevent unnecessary suffering. A study assessing nurses' knowledge and attitudes regarding pain management found that 89.5% of participants had insufficient knowledge and attitudes, with only 10.5% demonstrating adequate understanding. Younger nurses showed more positive attitudes, and previous pain management education significantly improved knowledge and attitudes. (1)

Figure (10) Classification of pain (2)**Physiology of Pain:**

Pain is a multifaceted physiological and emotional experience that is a critical protective mechanism, alerting the body to potential or actual tissue damage. The International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) defines pain as an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage. (3) The physiology of pain involves a complex interplay of peripheral and central pathways. Pain signals begin at nociceptors, specialized nerve endings that respond to high-intensity mechanical, thermal, or chemical stimuli. These are then transduced into electrical impulses by primary afferent neurons, specifically C and A-delta fibers. (4) These impulses travel to the dorsal horn of the spinal cord, where they synapse with second-order neurons. The signals are then transmitted via ascending pathways, such as the spinothalamic and

spinoreticular tracts, to the thalamus and the cortex for processing. The pain pathway is modulated by descending tracts involving the midbrain periaqueductal grey and nucleus raphe magnus, which can either amplify or inhibit pain signals. (4) Peripheral sensitization occurs at the injury site, leading to increased excitability of nociceptors. In contrast, central sensitization involves heightened central nervous system activity, contributing to hyperalgesia and allodynia. (5) Pain is a sensory experience and has significant emotional and psychological dimensions, which are processed in higher brain centers. The interaction between the nervous, immune, and endocrine systems further complicates the pain experience, as immune and glial cells can release pro-inflammatory cytokines that exacerbate pain. (6, 7) Despite advances in understanding pain physiology, effective pain

management remains challenging due to its complex nature and the variability in individual pain experiences. As highlighted by the International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP), the subjective nature of pain underscores the importance of considering sensory and emotional components in pain assessment and treatment. The role of neurotransmitters and neuropeptides, such as glutamate, substance P, and enkephalins, in modulating pain signals is crucial for developing targeted analgesic therapies. (4) Understanding the intricate pathways and mechanisms of pain can guide clinical approaches to more effectively manage pain, particularly in post-surgical settings where multimodal analgesia can simultaneously target multiple sites along the pain pathway. (8) The neurobiological and physiological changes in response to pain, including genetic factors and the impact of stress, further illustrate the complexity of pain as a biopsychosocial phenomenon. (7) Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of the physiology of pain is essential for developing better therapeutic strategies to alleviate suffering and improve the quality of life for individuals experiencing pain.

Assessment of Pain

Pain assessment is critical in clinical and research settings, necessitating various tools and scales to accurately gauge pain intensity, quality, and its impact on patients. The Behavioral Pain Scale (BPS) and the Critical Care Pain Observation Tool (CCPOT) are the most commonly used tools. These are particularly effective in assessing pain in mechanically ventilated and sedated ICU patients, including deep sedation patients. These tools have demonstrated good reliability and validity, making them suitable for use during painful procedures in the ICU. (9, 10) The Wong-Baker Faces Pain Rating Scale (WB-FPS) is highly recommended for pediatric patients due to its simplicity and ease of use, even for children as young as three. (11) In contrast, the Robert Packer Hospital/Functional Pain Scale (RPH/FPS) offers an objective assessment of pain and its impact on patient function. It strongly correlates with the Numeric Pain Scale (NPS) and the Wong-Baker Faces scale. (12) Tools like the Visual Analog Scale, Numeric Rating Scale, McGill Pain Questionnaire, and the Short Form 36 bodily pain subscale are widely used in rheumatologic and general pain populations. These tools help assess pain severity, location, quality, and pain-related interference in functioning. (13) For low back pain (LBP), specific tools such as the Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire (RMDQ) and Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) are noted for their construct validity and reliability. The Brief Pain

Inventory (BPI) is highly regarded for its responsiveness and validation for LBP. (14) Additionally, the Interventional Pain Assessment (IPA) tool, which simplifies pain assessment into three categories, has shown a strong correlation with the numerical rating scale (NRS) and is preferred by most patients for its simplicity and meaningful information on pain control. (15) Overall, the choice of pain assessment tool depends on the patient population, clinical setting, and specific needs of the assessment.

Nursing Role in Pain Management:

Nurses are pivotal in treating and managing pain, considered the fifth vital sign and a worldwide public health issue. Their responsibilities encompass both pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches to pain management. Nurses spend more time with patients than any other healthcare team member, making them crucial in assessing and managing pain effectively. There is a need for enhanced education and training programs to improve nurses' knowledge and practices in pain management. In addition to pharmacological methods, non-pharmacological therapies are essential and serve as complementary treatments to alleviate pain and anxiety in patients. These therapies include cognitive-behavioral, physical, and relaxation techniques, which nurses can administer or facilitate. (16) The role of nurses extends to ensuring effective communication between patients, their families, and the healthcare team, fostering a collaborative approach to pain management. This is particularly important in pediatric settings, where children may have difficulty articulating their pain, necessitating close observation and advocacy by nurses to ensure appropriate pain management (17). Despite the availability of various pain management methods, the prevalence of pain remains high in healthcare institutions, partly due to inadequate knowledge among nurses. A study conducted in Basra Teaching Hospital revealed that nearly half of the nurses had insufficient knowledge about pain management, underscoring the need for continuous education and training. (18) Moreover, nurses' perceptions and actions significantly influence the effectiveness of pain management strategies. An integrative literature review emphasized the importance of involving patients and their families in the treatment process, recommending reliable communication links and educational actions to enhance pain management outcomes. (16)

Pharmacological Interventions:

The optimal nursing role in pharmacological interventions for pain management is multifaceted, encompassing assessment, administration,

monitoring, and patient education. Nurses are pivotal in assessing pain, which is often complex and challenging to describe, necessitating appropriate assessment scales to ensure effective treatment, as discussed previously. In postoperative settings, nurses frequently assess pain and evaluate patient responses to pain management treatments, ensuring adherence to best practices to improve outcomes and quality of care. This includes the administration of pharmacological agents such as opioids, alpha-2 agonists, NMDA receptor antagonists, and other analgesics tailored to the specific needs of patients, taking into consideration where pain management is critical to prevent long-term negative impacts on neurodevelopment and quality of life. (19)

Non-Pharmacological Interventions

Nurses play a pivotal role in non-pharmacological pain management, leveraging their unique position within the healthcare team to provide holistic and patient-

centered care. Their responsibilities encompass a wide range of interventions, including massage, positioning, breathing exercises, music therapy, distraction, hydrotherapy, ambulation, relaxation exercises, aromatherapy, and acupuncture. (20) However, barriers such as lack of time, patient unwillingness, and patients' health beliefs can hinder the application of these techniques. Additionally, nurses' practice in non-pharmacological pain management is often limited by inadequate cooperation from physicians, heavy workloads, and insufficient nurse-to-patient ratios, contributing to a generally poor practice level among nurses. (21) Despite these challenges, non-pharmacological methods are particularly important for populations with high pain burdens and multiple chronic conditions, such as older adults and people with disabilities, where they are recommended as first-line therapies for chronic pain management.

Figure (2): Non-Pharmacological Techniques For Pain Management

CONCLUSION:

Pain management in nursing practice is an intricate and vital aspect that requires nurses to possess sufficient expertise and competencies. To achieve successful pain management outcomes, nurses must utilize suitable evaluation instruments and a blend of pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical measures. Continuous learning opportunities and training sessions are imperative to guarantee that nurses can deliver top-notch healthcare services and enhance patients' overall well-being. Nurses must stay updated on the latest developments in pain management techniques and strategies to provide optimal care and promote positive patient results.

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